

CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES ON SILVER TUNGSTATES

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When AgNO_3 is added to Na_2WO_4 , various silver tungstates are formed, depending on the f_H of the medium. Normal silver tungstate, $\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{WO}_3$, is formed at p_H 8-10. From weakly acid solutions of p_H 5.5 to 7.0 silver ditungstate, $\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{WO}_3$ is obtained. Silver metatungstate having the composition $\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot 4\text{WO}_3$ is formed from acid solutions at p_H 4 to 5.

Meagre references are available in literature to the study of the reaction between AgNO_3 and Na_2WO_4 at different p_H s of the solution. Normal silver tungstate was prepared by Zettnow *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 2930) by treating a normal sodium tungstate with AgNO_3 . Rosenheim and Kohn (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 69, 247) and Copaux (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1909, 17, 217; 1912, 28, 22) prepared various insoluble salts by double decomposition and they pointed out that metatungstates had the structure of heteropoly acids. There is, however, hardly any reference to the study of this reaction at different p_H s of the solution by physicochemical methods. In the absence of any detailed study of these silver tungstates, it was considered worth while to investigate these silver complexes at different H^+ -ion concentrations of the medium by electrometric methods, so as to obtain more conclusive evidences on their composition. In the present paper, only the results of conductometric titrations have been included and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Merck's guaranteed extra pure reagents, AgNO_3 and Na_2WO_4 , were used. Air-free conductivity water was used for the preparation of standard solutions and further dilutions. Sodium tungstate was estimated as barium tungstate (Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis, 1953, p. 492). The conductivities were measured by the Kohlrausch Universal Bridge (W. G. Pye, Ltd.). The alternating current was supplied by a low frequency oscillator (1000 c/s) and the point of balance was indicated by minima of sound in the head phone. The titration cell was immersed in an electrically maintained thermostat. The conductance obtained after each addition was corrected for the dilution effect by multiplying the observed conductance by V/X , where V refers to total volume of the solution and X c.c. is the volume of the reactant already taken in the cell (Dayies, "Conductivity of Solutions", p. 239). The curves were plotted between the corrected conductance, thus obtained, and the volume of the titrant, using different concentrations of the reactants. The titrations were carried out by both direct and reverse methods (*i.e.*, when Na_2WO_4 solution from the micro-burette was added to AgNO_3 solution in the conductivity cell and *vice versa*). Titrations were also performed in varying concentrations of alcohol; 20 c.c. of the reagent was taken in the cell each time (Table I).

TABLE I

Molarity of Na_2WO_4	Molarity of AgNO_3	Points showing breaks in				Formula supported.	
		Aqueous soln.		Alcoholic soln.			
		Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.		
Direct titrations (Fig. 1). $p_H = 8-8.5$.							
0.0333 M	0.01 M	3.0 c.c.	2.85 c.c.	2.7 c.c.	2.65 in 10% alc. 2.4 in 20% alc.	} $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{WO}_3$	
0.05	0.5	4.0	3.90	3.6 3.2	2.4 in 20% alc. 3.50 in 10% alc. 3.20 in 20% alc.		
Reverse titrations (Fig. 2). $p_H = 8-8.5$.							
Titrations in presence of acids (Fig. 3). $p_H = 6$.							
0.225	0.2	2.5	2.45	2.25 2.00	2.2 in 10% alc. 2.0 in 20% alc.	} $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot 2\text{WO}_3$	
0.5	0.2	2.5	2.40	2.25 2.00	$p_H = 4.6$ (Fig. 4). 2.20 in 10% alc. 2.00 in 20% alc.		} $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot 4\text{WO}_3$

DISCUSSION

AgNO_3 was found to have p_H 5.6-5.9. The p_H of the Na_2WO_4 was 9.4 and, hence, in solution it behaved strongly alkaline. In alkaline solution only the species WO_4^{2-} ion is said to exist (Emeleus and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", 1952, p. 212). This is confirmed by the formation of normal silver tungstate, $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{WO}_3$, in the alkaline range.

It will be observed from conductometric titration curves in Fig. 2 and the summary of observations in Table I, that one sharp point of intersection is obtained corresponding to the formation of normal silver tungstate, having the composition $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{WO}_3$ from p_H range of 8 to 10. In direct titrations, Ag_2WO_4 is precipitated and NaNO_3 is formed. Since the ionic mobility of $\text{Na}^+ < \text{Ag}^+$, the conductivity slightly decreases when precipitation is complete; further addition of Na_2WO_4 results in an increase of conductivity (Fig. 1). (The ionic mobilities of Ag^+ , Na^+ and NO_3^- are 63.5, 50.9 and 70.6 respectively.) In reverse titrations (Fig. 2), the conductivity rises from the beginning as the ionic mobility of $2\text{NO}_3^- > \text{WO}_4^{2-}$, and after complete precipitation it further increases due to excess of AgNO_3 . In very dilute solutions (0.002 M- Na_2WO_4 and 0.01 M- Ag) the conductivity due to solubility of Ag_2WO_4 interferes with the results. The solubility of Ag_2WO_4 is 0.0266 g./litre and the solubility product on determination is found to be 6.12×10^{-12} at 27°.

Definite amounts of solutions of Na_2WO_4 of known strengths were brought to various p_H values by suitable additions of HNO_3 and the p_H was measured by using a glass electrode. The tungstate ion is said to exist in the different states of aggregation, depending on the p_H of the medium, according to Jander *et al.* (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1951, 265, 244). When AgNO_3 is added to Na_2WO_4 at a p_H range from 5.5 to 6.5 and more acidic range 4 to 5, respectively and the conductance measured and plotted against the volume of the titrant, one distinct break is obtained in both cases, corresponding to the formation of $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot 2\text{WO}_3$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot 4\text{WO}_3$ respectively. In each case the precipitated silver tungstate was analysed for Ag and W contents by standard methods of analysis. The compounds were found to have the same composition. No precipitation on addition of AgNO_3 took place below p_H 4.

FIG. 2
Reverse conductometric titration.

FIG. 1
Direct conductometric titration.

FIG. 4
 $p_H = 4.61$

FIG. 3
 $p_H = 6.0$

0.2M AgNO_3 added (c.c.) to 20 c.c. of 0.025M Na_3WO_4 containing 1 mol. of acid.

It may further be noted (Table 1) that the values in aqueous-alcoholic media gradually approach the theoretical values. The silver tungstate is colloidal in nature. The role of alcohol is to decrease the solubility of the precipitate and, hence, a closer approach to the theoretical values is envisaged in the experimental results, when titrations are performed in aqueous-alcoholic media.

The analytical work on the composition of various silver tungstates is under investigation and the results will be communicated later.

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